

ORGANIC REACTIONS WITH POLYPHOSPHORIC ACID. PART III. ONE-STEP ACYLATION AND ALKYLATION: *cyclopentenones*

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Polyphosphoric acid has been shown to be a useful reagent for the one-step synthesis of certain cyclic systems which had been prepared previously through several intermediate stages. Possible mechanistic features of the reaction have been discussed.

Nazarov and co-workers (*Bull. Acad. Sci. U. S. S. R., Cl. Sci. Chim.*, 1946, 633; 1947, 205; *J. Gen. Chem.*, U.S.S.R. 1950, 20, 2009, 2079, 2091) have demonstrated that a variety of allylvinyl and divinyl ketones undergo an acid-catalysed ring-closure to yield substituted *cyclopentenones*. The most useful reagent for this purpose has been found to be a phosphoric acid-formic acid mixture. It appeared that polyphosphoric acid (PPA) could be utilised with advantage for such Nazarov cyclisations. Since PPA had been shown to be capable of effecting intermolecular acylations (Sukh Dev, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1954, 1071; this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 703) it was thought worthwhile to investigate the acylation of *cycloalkenes* with suitable unsaturated acids, as the resulting primary products of acylation could possibly undergo ring-closure under the conditions of the reaction to furnish directly the substituted *cyclopentenones*. This one-step acylation and alkylation reaction has been realised and forms the subject matter of the present communication (cf. Sukh Dev, *loc. cit.*, 1954).

The Friedel-Crafts reaction between an acid chloride of an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated acid and an aromatic hydrocarbon is known to produce substituted *cyclopentenones* in certain cases (Kohler, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1909, 42, 375; Auwers, *Ber.*, 1921, 54, 987; Auwers and Risse, *Annalen*, 1933, 502, 282; Baker and Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 787; Herz, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 73). The same reaction, when carried out on an acid instead of its chloride, results in alkylation only (Eijkman, *Chem. Weekblad.*, 1907, 4, 727; 1908, 5, 655). The Friedel-Crafts interaction between a *cycloalkene* and an unsaturated acid chloride leads to the formation of the corresponding dichloro ketones contaminated to some extent with the corresponding chlorovinyl ketones; these intermediates resist cyclisation under the conditions of the reaction (Baddeley *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 124).

Bicyclo -[4 : 3 : 0]-*nonane System*

On treatment of *cyclohexene* with acrylic acid in PPA, the expected 4:5:6:7-tetrahydroindan-1-one (I) (Sukh Dev, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 255 and the references cited therein) was readily obtained in 16% yield. As anticipated, the reaction between crotonic acid and *cyclohexene* was more facile and 3-methyl-4:5:6:7-tetrahydroindan-1-one (II) could be obtained in yields of 55-60%. This compound was obtained previously

by Nazarov and Pinkina (*Bull. Acad. Sci. U.S.S.R., Cl. Sci. Chim.*, 1946, 633), and Hamlet *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 2652) by the vinyl-acetylene method involving three steps; similarly Braude and Coles (*ibid.*, 1952, 1430) synthesised it by a new four-step reaction sequence in an overall yield of about 19%.

The condensation of cinnamic acid with *cyclohexene* yielded a ketone in 25% yield. As will be clear from the reaction mechanism discussed below, this unsaturated ketone can possibly have a structure (III), (IV) or (V); the last structure represents the product of simple acylation. Since the product displayed its $\alpha\beta$ unsaturated ketone absorption peak at $238\text{ m}\mu$ (ϵ 13150), which is almost the same as that of (I) (λ_{max} $237\text{ m}\mu$) or (II) (λ_{max} $238\text{ m}\mu$), the structure (III) has been assigned to this compound; the chromophore present in (IV) or (V) should show this band at about $280\text{ m}\mu$ (cf. Kuhn and Staab, *Ber.*, 1954, 87, 262).

(I: R = H;
 (II: R = Me)
 (III: R = Ph)

(IV)

(V)

The reaction between benzoic anhydride and *cyclohexene* afforded a ketone in 35-40% yield, which from its properties has been identified with the hexahydrofluorenone (VI) of Cook and Hewett (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 71; cf. Braude and Forbes, *ibid.*, 1953, 2208). To show the benzoyl*cyclohexene* (VII) to be a possible intermediate, it was treated with PPA, when the cyclised ketone (VI) was obtained in 65% yield.

(VI)

(VII)

Bicyclo-[3:3:0]-octane System

cyclopentene and crotonic acid react in the presence of PPA to yield a bicyclic ketone (22% yield), which has been characterised as 1-methyl-bicyclo-[3:3:0]- Δ^7 -octen-3-one (VIII). This compound was obtained previously by Nazarov and Burmistrova (*Bull. Acad. Sci. U.S.S.R., Cl. Sci. Chim.*, 1947, 51) in an overall yield of

ca. 18% by a three-step sequence of reactions. The properties of this compound, as reported by these authors, are slightly different (vide Experimental) from those determined now. The structure (VIII) for our product is in accord with its U.V. light absorption (λ_{max} 241 $m\mu$; ϵ 12100); an $\alpha\beta$ -trisubstituted cyclopentenone is expected to display its principal band at $236 \pm 5m\mu$ (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 259 and the

(VIII)

(IX)

(X)

references cited therein). In the infra-red the compound showed peaks at 1665 cm^{-1} ($\nu_{C=O}$) and 1622 cm^{-1} ($\nu_{C=C}$), which are characteristic of an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketone with a *transoid*-system (Jones and Sandorf in Weissberger's "Technique of Organic Chemistry", Interscience Publishers, 1956, Vol. IX, p. 481; Braude and Timmons, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 3766). As expected, the compound on quantitative catalytic hydrogenation consumed one mole equivalent of hydrogen to furnish a saturated dihydroketone (IX), which was stereochemically almost completely homogeneous. From the fact that the bicyclo-[3:3:0]-octane system is far more stable in the *cis*-configuration (Cook and Linstead, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 946; Barrett and Linstead, *ibid.*, 1935, 438; 1936, 611) and that in catalytic hydrogenation at room temperature and pressure the hydrogen adsorbed on the surface of the catalyst effects a simultaneous *cis*-attack on the least sterically hindered side of the unsaturated substrate (Farkas and Farkas, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1937, 33, 837; Linstead *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 63, 1985), the dihydroketone has been assigned the *cis-syn* configuration (IX). In the infra-red the dihydroketone displayed its carbonyl stretching frequency at 1725 cm^{-1} . This value lies intermediate between those expected of a cyclohexanone (1720 to 1706 cm^{-1}) and a cyclopentanone derivative (1740 to 1749 cm^{-1} ; Bellamy, "The Infra-red Spectra of Complex Molecules", Methuen & Co., London, 1954, p. 127). The far less likely cyclohexenone structure (X) * for the original condensation product has been ruled out by a straightforward synthesis of (VIII), accomplished in connection with some other investigation, to be reported later.

DISCUSSION

The activity of polyphosphoric acid for various acid-catalysed transformations and cyclisations (Uhlig, *Angew. Chem.*, 1954, 66, 435) is undoubtedly due to the polar phosphorus pentoxide (XIV) made available in an ionising medium.

* Theoretically (cf. Discussion), the condensation of crotonic acid with cyclopentene can possibly give rise to the cyclohexenone derivative (X): (Contd. next page).

The dissolution of an organic acid in PPA should rapidly and reversibly lead to the formation of the preliminary co-ordination complex (XV), which stabilises itself by the electron-interactions indicated to give the ions shown in (XVI); it may be noted that the anion in (XVI) is stabilised by resonance.

(XIV)

(XV)

(XVI)

Thus, a solution of an organic acid in PPA would be a potent source of acylium ions.

In the case of the results discussed in the present communication, the oxocarbenium ion (XVII) would be stabilised by resonance; however the sterically-strained species (XVIIb) would not contribute appreciably. Its attack on an olefinic linkage should give the thermodynamically preferred intermediate (XVIII)**, which stabilises itself by the

*

(XI)

(XII)

(XIII)

but this is unlikely as the equilibrium should be very largely in favour of (XI). It is of interest to note that both (XI; Braude and Forbes, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 2108) and (XII; Nazarov and Barmistrova, *loc. cit.*) have been found to cyclise to (XIII) on treatment with phosphoric acid, and further that Braude and Forbes (*loc. cit.*) failed to effect the Nazarov cyclisation of (XI) to (VIII) with a mixture of phosphoric and formic acids.

** That this carbonium ion has a fairly long life is indicated by its ability to undergo a Wagner-Meerwein type rearrangement wherever possible. Thus cycloheptene and acetic or crotonic acid do not yield the normal expected products.

It may be further noted that (XIII) can directly undergo ring-closure according to the Nazarov-Braude mechanism discussed later.

(XVIII)

(XIX)

(XX)

(XXI)

elimination of a proton to yield the divinyl ketone (XIX). The fact that a carbonium ion of type (XX) is unimportant in these reactions conducted in PPA, is borne out by the results of the interaction of an unsaturated acid (e.g. crotonic acid) and anisole. In this case only *p*-methoxycrotonophenone was obtained (80% yield) and none of 3-methyl-6-methoxyindan-1-one, which would have ultimately resulted from an attack of (XX), was detected (Sukh Dev, *loc. cit.*, 1956).

The divinyl ketone then undergoes ring-closure to yield the corresponding cyclopentenone. Mechanism for the cyclisation of vinylallyl and divinyl ketones has been discussed (Nazarov and Kotlyarevskii, *J. Gen. Chem. U.S.S.R.*, 1950, 20, 1501; Kirsanov *et al.*, *Bull. Acad. Sci. U.S.S.R., Cl. Sci. Chim.*, 1953, 114; Braude and Coles, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 1430). These authors assume the addition of the proton (in the case of the PPA, a proton or P_2O_5 itself can be considered as the active cyclising agent) to the propenyl or vinyl side-chain to give the carbonium ion (XXI) which cyclises as shown.

It can be seen that in the cyclisation of (XXI), the carbonium ion has attacked the electron-deficient end of the $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated carbonyl system, and as such, should not be very effective. Moreover, the carbonyl oxygen is much more basic and it is known (Stoll and co-workers, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1955, 38, 1573, 1593; 1956, 39, 183, 200; Meinwald and Grossman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 992) that if the resulting oxycarbonium ion (or its vinyllog) is geometrically and sterically suitably situated with respect to the ethylenic linkage, it attacks it intramolecularly. In view of these considerations the following mechanism (cf. Erickson, M.I.T. Seminar in Organic Chemistry, 1954-55, 81; Braude and Coles, *loc. cit.*), which satisfies these points, appears more reasonable and is depicted for the cyclisation of crotonoyl- Δ^1 -cyclohexene (XXII) :

Step A (fast):

Step B (slow):

Step C (fast):

In the cyclised carbonium ion (XXIV) the canonical structure (a) with a vacant *p*-orbital on a tertiary carbon should be of greater importance to the hybrid. Furthermore, since the step (C) is reversible, the final product under the conditions of the reaction should be thermodynamically equilibrated. In these cyclisations, the final product has always been found to have a structure of type (II), which should indicate a far greater stability of the structure (II) as compared to (XXVI); compounds of type (XXVI) have been isolated in cases where a proton-elimination to give the type (II) is not possible (Nazarov and Pinkina, *J. Gen. Chem. U.S.S.R.*, 1950, **20**, 2079; Nazarov and Burmistrova *ibid.*, 1950, **20**, 2091).

EXPERIMENTAL

Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Petroleum ether refers to the fraction of b.p. 40° - 60° . Anhydrous sodium sulphate was used for drying the extracts. The ultraviolet light absorptions were measured in 95% ethanolic solution on a Beckman DU spectrophotometer.

4:5:6:7-Tetrahydroindan-1-one (I).—To PPA (from 70 g. of P_2O_5 and 30 c.c. of orthophosphoric acid of *d* 1.75; Sukh Dev, this *Journal*, 1955, **32**, 262), maintained at $57^{\circ} \pm 2^{\circ}$ in a three-necked flask (250 c.c.) carrying a Hershberg stirrer and a reflux

condenser and protected from access of moisture, were introduced in one lot cyclohexene (8.2 g., 0.1 M) and glacial acrylic acid (7.2 g., 0.1 M). The reaction mixture was vigorously stirred at that temperature for a total of 30 mins. The reddish brown product, while still hot, was at once poured on ice (ca. 200 g.) and water. After the decomposition of the complex, the mixture was diluted to 400 c.c. (ca.) with water and after dissolving in ammonium sulphate (75 g.) was extracted with petroleum ether (40 c.c. $\times$ 3). In case there was any polymerised material, insoluble in petroleum ether, that was rejected. The solvent extract was washed with water (50 c.c.); then with aqueous ammonium hydroxide (5% ; 50 c.c. $\times$ 2) and finally with brine (50 c.c.) and dried. The solvent was removed and the residue fractionated : after a forerun (0.3 g.) the desired ketone (I) was collected at 125-27°/12 mm (2.2 g., 16.2% ; n_D^{25} 1.5170) and a polymeric residue (ca. 7 g.) remained.

The ketone was characterised as its 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (HCl method). Yield of the crude derivative of m.p. 221-24° was 85% ; recrystallisation from xylene gave dark red shining leaflets, m.p. 229-30° (Sukh Dev, *loc. cit.*, m.p. 229-30°), the m.p. remained undepressed on admixture with an authentic sample.

3-Methyl-4 : 5 : 6 : 7-tetrahydroindan-1-one (II).—When in the above experiment acrylic acid was replaced by an equivalent quantity of crotonic acid (8.6 g.) and the resulting dark red complex worked up as above, the bicyclic ketone (II) was obtained as a colorless oil, b.p. 152-55°/42 mm, n_D^{25} 1.5100, yield 9.0 g. (60%). The central cut of a refractionated sample had b.p. 130°/15 mm, 115°/4 mm, 106°/2.5 mm ; n_D^{25} 1.5105 ; λ_{max} 238 μ (ϵ 13240) (Hamlet *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, record b.p. 84-86°/1 mm, n_D^{25} 1.5150 ; λ_{max} 238 μ , ϵ 12500).

The semicarbazone (pyridine method) (m.p. of crude product, 209-212° decomp.) on two crystallisations from alcohol furnished white lustrous leaflets and flat needles, m.p. 216-17° (decomp.) (Braude and Coles, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. 214-17°).

The 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (H₂SO₄ method) (m.p. of crude : 228-30°) on one crystallisation from acetic acid, followed by two recrystallisations from xylene, was obtained in dark red needles, m.p. 244° (decomp.) (Braude and Coles, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. 246-48° corr.).

3-Phenyl-4 : 5 : 6 : 7-tetrahydroindan-1-one (III) was similarly prepared by using finely powdered cinnamic acid (14.8 g., 0.1 M) in the above condensation. The complex was dark brown in colour and the product was extracted with ether (60 c.c. $\times$ 3) instead of petroleum ether. After a small forerun (0.5 g.), the required product was obtained as a viscous, pale yellow liquid of b.p. 162-65°/1.2 mm (n_D^{25} 1.5800 ; yield 5.5 g., 25.9%) and the polymeric residue amounted to 5 g. (ca.). (Found : C, 84.8 ; H, 7.8. C₁₅H₁₆O requires C, 84.9 ; H, 7.54%).

The semicarbazone (pyridine method) (crude m.p. 214-15°) on three crystallisations from pyridine-alcohol mixture yielded colorless, transparent rectangular sheets, m.p. 220-21° with effervescence. (Found : N, 15.5. C₁₄H₁₆ON₃ requires N, 15.6%).

The 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (HCl method) (crude m.p. 163-65°) was best recrystallised from benzene—*n*-hexane mixture to furnish red prismatic rods, m.p. 173-74°. (Found : N, 14.5. C₂₁H₂₀O₄N₄ requires N, 14.3%).

Hexahydrofluorenone (VI): (i) *From cyclohexene and Benzoic Anhydride.*—To PPA (P_2O_5 , 70 g. and H_3PO_4 , 30 c.c.) at $57^\circ \pm 2^\circ$ a mixture of cyclohexene (8.2 g., 0.1 M) and benzoic anhydride (11.3 g., 0.05 M; the anhydride was preferred over the acid because of the much lower m.p. of the former) was added and the reaction carried out as described above. The complex was brown-red in colour and the extraction was carried out with ether. The crude product was fractionated first to get the cut of b.p. $115-25^\circ/0.5$ mm (9.0 g.), which was carefully refractionated, b.p. $118-22^\circ/0.5$ mm, yield 7.5 g. (41.6%). The product solidified on cooling in ice and was obtained in white prismatic rods by recrystallisation from petroleum ether at 10° , m.p. $42-42.5^\circ$, yield 2.8 g. The mother-liquor on working up yielded the crude ketone (4.3 g.) which gave the same semicarbazone (4.0 g., *vide infra*). Light absorption: λ_{max} 245 m μ (ϵ 12, 240) (Cook and Hewett, *loc. cit.*, record b.p. $126-29^\circ/0.8$ mm, m.p. $41.5-42^\circ$).

The semicarbazone (pyridine method) (crude: m.p. $203-205^\circ$) was recrystallised twice from alcohol to furnish white felted needles, m.p. $213-14^\circ$ (Cook and Hewett, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. $212-13^\circ$).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (H_2SO_4 method) (crude: m.p. $185-88^\circ$) on crystallisation from acetic acid furnished brick-red, lustrous flat needles, m.p. $190-91^\circ$ (Braude and Forbes, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. $190-91^\circ$).

(ii) *From Benzoyl- Δ^1 -cyclohexene.*—Benzoylcyclohexene was prepared by the method of Christ and Fuson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 893). The material (b.p. $151-53^\circ/6$ mm, n_D^{20} 1.5580) prepared by this method could not be obtained in the crystalline state unlike the preparation of Braude and Forbes (*loc. cit.*). However, it could be purified *via* its semicarbazido-semicarbazone. This was prepared by allowing the ketone to react with two equivalents of semicarbazide hydrochloride in aqueous-alcoholic-pyridine solution; recrystallisation from dilute alcohol yielded colorless, prismatic rods and cubes, m.p. $206-207^\circ$ with effervescence. (Found: N, 26.38, 26.42. $C_{13}H_{22}O_2N_6$ requires N, 26.42%). The regeneration of the ketone was effected by refluxing the well-powdered material (6.2 g.) with oxalic acid (10 g. in 200 c.c. of water) and *n*-heptane (50 c.c.) for 18 hours. Working up in that usual way yielded the ketone: b.p. $124^\circ/0.75$ mm, n_D^{20} 1.5685, m.p. 37° (from pet. ether at -10°), yield 2.5 g., λ_{max} 246 m μ (ϵ 13080). 2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone, bright orange-red leaflets from benzene-*n*-hexane, m.p. $166-68^\circ$ (Braude and Forbes, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. 38° , n_D^{20} 1.5660; λ_{max} 247 m μ , ϵ 12000; 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone m.p. 168°).

A mixture of PPA (from P_2O_5 , 7 g. and phosphoric acid, 3 c.c.) and benzoylcyclohexene (1 g.) was heated on the steam-bath for 15 minutes and then worked up to yield the hexahydrofluorenone, b.p. $160-61^\circ/4$ mm, m.p. $41-42^\circ$, yield 0.65 g. Mixed m.p. with a sample from method (i) was undepressed.

3-Methyl-bicyclo-[3:3:0]- Δ^7 :⁸octen-1-one (VIII).—To PPA (from P_2O_5 , 70 g. and phosphoric acid, 30 c.c.) at $40^\circ \pm 2^\circ$ cyclopentene (6.8 g., 0.1 M) and crotonic acid (8.6 g., 0.1 M) were added and efficiently stirred at this temperature for one hour. The deep brownish red product was worked up as detailed for (I). The ketone was

obtained as a colorless liquid, b.p. 85-92°/3 mm, n_D^{20} 1.5010, yield 3.0 g. It was purified through its semicarbazone (*vide infra*) by the oxalic acid—*n*-heptane method (4½ hours' refluxing) to afford pure (VIII), b.p. 91-92°/4 mm, n_D^{20} 1.5015 (Nazarov and Burmistrova, *loc. cit.*, record b.p. 78-78.5°/4 mm., n_D^{20} 1.5060). (Found: C, 79.28 H, 8.91. C₉H₁₂O requires C, 79.41; H, 8.9%).

The *semicarbazone* (pyridine method) (crude: m.p. 210-11°) was crystallised twice from a mixture of pyridine and alcohol to furnish colorless flat needles, m.p. 216-17° (decomp.) (Nazarov and Burmistrova, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. 201°). (Found: N, 22.1. C₁₀H₁₅ON₃ requires N, 21.8%).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (sulphuric acid method) was obtained as fine dark red needles from a mixture of acetic acid and alcohol, m.p. 214-15°. (Found: N, 17.9. C₁₃H₁₆O₄N₄ requires N, 17.7%).

3-Methyl-cis-bicyclo-[3:3:0]-octan-1-one (IX).—The above ketone (3.1 g.) was hydrogenated at room temperature and pressure over prerduced Pd CaCO₃ catalyst (0.5 g.) in alcohol (25 c.c.). The hydrogen uptake ceased after (45 mins.) the absorption of 95% of the theoretical volume of hydrogen, when the catalyst was removed by filtration and washed with ether (50 c.c.). From the combined filtrates the solvents were fractionated off and the residue distilled to furnish the dihydroketone (IX) as a colorless liquid with a camphoraceous odour: b. p. 87-88°/9.5 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4700, yield 3.0 g. (Nazarov and Burmistrova, *loc. cit.*, record b. p. 83-84°/11 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4738). (Found: C, 77.9; H, 10.1. C₉H₁₄O requires C, 78.2; H, 10.1%).

The *semicarbazone* was prepared by the pyridine method (crude: m. p. 184-86°). Recrystallisation from dilute alcohol gave white needles, m.p. 186-87° (Nazarov and Burmistrova, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. 178-79°). (Found: N, 21.3. C₁₀H₁₇ON₃ requires N, 21.5%).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (HCl method) was crystallised from a mixture of benzene and *n*-hexane to furnish rosettes of orange-yellow needles, m.p. 161-62°. (Found: N, 17.2. C₁₅H₁₈O₄N₄ requires N, 17.6%).

Infra-red spectra were measured by the courtesy of Samuel P. Sadtler & Son Inc. (Philadelphia) on a Baird Associates I.R. spectrophotometer (NaCl prism) using pure liquids in 0.01 mm cell.